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ZR, HF, Y AND REE IN ROCKS OF THE NOVOKOSTANTYNIIVKA U DEPOSIT (CENTRAL UKRAINE)

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ABSTRACT

The concentrations of Zr, Hf, Y and REE in rocks of the Novokostantynivka albitite-type U deposit in Ukraine were investigated. In host granites, the element concentrations are found to be typical of granites, with close to chondritic values of Zr/Hf (35.8 – 44.0) and Y/Ho (27.3 – 28.4) ratios and chondrite-normalized REE+Y patterns having uniform Eu minimums. La/Yb ratio ranges from 9.7 to 117.4 with strong linear correlation between La and Yb. The elements disproportionation is observed in metasomatically altered rocks although no changes of REE+Y patterns are visible. Heavy REE accumulation was revealed in the richest uraninite ores only. Hydrothermal input resulted in crystallization of zircon-malacoon and uranium mineralization with increasing Zr/Hf ratios up to 120.5 in albitites and direct correlation between Zr and U. Redistribution of Zr and Hf is connected to Ca-metasomatism stage later superimposed on albitite bodies.

Keywords: uranium ores, Novokostantynivka deposit, albitites, metasomatism, Ukraine, ore geochemistry, rare elements, rare earth elements.

Introduction. U deposits related to sodium metasomatism are found throughout the world [1, 2, 3]. The largest, and well explored deposits occur in Ukraine where they were first discovered about 80 years ago. Presently, the Central Ukraine U Province (CUUP) comprises about 20 U deposits and numerous U showings related to the Paleoproterozoic Na-metasomatism **Помилка! Джерело посилання не знайдено..** The Novokostantynivka U deposit was discovered in 1975 and is the largest containing 104 th. t of U₃O₈ [4].

Research information on geology, mineralogy and ore forming parameters of the Novokostantynivka U deposit is described in earlier papers [3]. Zr, Hf, Y and REE and their ratios are sensitive petrological indicators which is not well investigated in relation to metasomatic processes and U ore accumulations. Previous few studies on trace elements in ores are very old and limited by low precision of analysis [1]. From trace element investigation Cuney et al. [3] found that U accumulated with rising U/Th ratio in comparison with host granites, whereas Zr/Hf ratio reaches suprachondritic values in albitites, but HREE not significantly redistributed in metasomatic bodies of the deposit. The present study goals to investigate behaviors of Zr, Hf, Y and REE during Na metasomatism and ore accumulation in the Novokostantynivka U and their relation to the metasomatic processes.

Geological pattern. The Novokostantynivka U deposit is found on the area 1.5×1.5 km in northern central part of the Novoukrainka batholith near its northern tectonic contact with the Korsun-Novomyrhorod pluton (Fig. 1). The Novoukrainka granite batholith covers an area of ~3500 km² and is surrounded by numerous smaller granite intrusions emplaced at 2039±6 – 2025±48 Ma [3]. The batholith includes wide spectrum of magmatic rocks varying from quartz diorites and quartz monzonites to quartz syenites and granites [4]. Red porphyritic coarse-grained garnet-biotite granites and adamellites are the most widespread rocks which compose 70-80 % of the Novoukrainka complex. The Novoukrainka granitoids are primarily foliated due to a conspicuous alignment of the large microcline megacrysts, suggesting about magma crystallization at regional stress [3, 4].

Intense metasomatic alterations of the Novoukrainka granites in the deposit extend along zones of cataclasis developed in place of intersection of Secant and Western faults of N-E striking Glodok regional fault zone with a series of shear zones of the meridionally striking Novokostantynivka tectonic zone [3]. The deposit includes 178 lens-, bed- and stockwork-type ore bodies localized within 3 ore zones [3]. U ores were found by boreholes down to -1200 m.

Fig. 1. Geological position of the Novokostantynivka deposit. 1 – Korsun-Novomyrhorod basites and ultrabasites; 2 – Korsun-Novomyrhorod rapakivi pluton; 3 – Kirovograd granites, 4 – Novoukrainka batholith; 5 – Ingul-Inguletsk gneisses; 6 – regional faults; 7 – albitite-type U deposits (NK – Novokostantynivka U deposit).

Techniques. Rock samples were selected in underground mines and from drill cores. Sampled rocks were comprehensively investigated and described during sampling and when in the lab. Samples were cut and then prepared as double-polished and thick sections for examination of mineral paragenesis using optical microscopy.

Part of samples, after agate mortar crushing were analysed with ICP-AES/-MS techniques at SARM, CRPG in Nancy (France) for 11 major and 44 trace elements. The geochemical interpretation is based on published experimental and statistical data on the behavior of elements in rocks and media.

Mineralogical characteristics and mineral-forming stages. Metasomatically altered rocks in the

deposit commonly consist of albitites with different amount of femic minerals. Aegirine, aegirine-riebeckite, aegirine-actinolite, chlorite-epidote and phlogopite-calcite albitites, and their mixed varieties are most common in the deposit. Albitites are widely surrounded by dequartzified granites representing the earliest external zones of metasomatic alteration [3].

The deposit was formed during 5 stages produced successive hydrothermal mineralisation [3]: (i) selective quartz leaching from the host granites = episyenitization; (ii) Na-metasomatism = albitisation; (iii) Ca-metasomatism = epidotisation, actinolization and carbonatization; (iv) K-metasomatism = phlogopitization accompanied by the richest U-mineralization; (v) hy-

drolysis = chloritization. Major U deposition is connected with the hydrothermal event started from tectonic fracturation of Na-metasomatites [4]. The invasion of new hydrothermal solutions resulted in Ca- (stage iii) and K- (stage iv) metasomatic alterations providing successive deposition of andradite–titanite–epidote, actinolite–calcite and calcite-phlogopite parageneses. Uraninite, brannerite and davidite are major U-minerals, occur as rare veinlets and disseminated and

form the most highly graded ores in calcite-phlogopite-magnetite albitites.

Aegirine replaces zircon in albitites (Fig. 2a) and thus zircon was unstable during Na-metasomatism stage. Zircon-malacon often occur in mineralized albitites as veinlets and overgrows on magmatic zircon crystals, and contains fine inclusions of uraninite (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2. Mineral interrelations in the Novokostantynivka deposit: (a) aegirine replaces magmatic zircon phenocryst in albitite; (b) malacon (darker) and uraninite overgrows on magmatic zircon; ab – albitite, eg – aegirine, mg - magnetite, u – uraninite, zr – zircon.

The metasomatic bodies are complicatedly zoned in accordance with the above-described stages. Later mineral associations commonly intersect and replace earlier metasomatic bodies in their core parts and also along later cracks and zones of fracturation.

Zr and Hf. In high grade ores of the Novokostantynivka deposit, predominantly represented by phlogopite-calcite-magnetite albitites, U and Zr show strong positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.95$) (Fig. 3a), from the lowest values in the host granites to U-rich ores containing the highest amounts of both U and Zr.

Fig. 3. Element interrelations in the Novokostantynivka deposit.

U vs Zr in joint ore body 1-21 – 1-29.

Th/U vs Zr/Hf. 1 – granites, 2 – episyenites, 2-5: albitites of different U grade: 3 - < 0.05 wt.%, 4 – 0.05-0.2 wt.%, 5 - > 0.2 wt.%.

Zr/Hf ratios range from 35.8 to 37.2 mostly (Fig. 3b) and locally increase up to 44.0. These values are close to the chondritic ratio 37.1 [5] which should be characteristic of the Earth mantle [6]. In host granites, Zr correlates with Hf (Fig. 5a).

Zr/Hf ratios of episyenites range from 34.1 to 45.5 (Fig. 3a), are similar to those in granites.

In U-mineralized albitites Zr/Hf ratios vary widely from those found in granites to suprachondritic values ($34.3 < \text{Zr/Hf} < 120.5$) (Fig. 3a).

Zr/Hf - Th/U diagram clearly shows an increase in the Zr/Hf ratio from the values characterising the host

Novoukrainka granites to episyenites and albitites (Fig. 3b). Two concentration peaks of Zr/Hf ratios are visible

on the diagram: (i) up to 121 in episyenites and low grade albitites at Th/U ratio from 0.02 to 0.03; (ii) up to 50-85 in the mineralized albitites (U content is from 0.2 to 6.3 wt.%, with high grade ores in phlogopite-calcite albitites) at Th/U ratio of ~0.01. Zr/Hf ratio depends on Zr content with little variation of Hf in the rocks. Mineralogically, it is reflected by progressive disproportionation of Zr and Hf (Fig. 5a) due to crystallization of hydrothermal zircon.

Y and REE. Chondrite-normalized REE+Y pattern is similar both in host granites, episyenites and different albitites, having a minimum of Eu (Fig. 4). However, with increasing U content, concentration of heavy REE and Y is increased also (Fig. 4), and with further increasing U content over 1 wt%, the chondrite-normalized patterns become similar to found in high grade uraninite samples (Fig. 4). This suggests that uraninite is the main mineral containing RRE and Y in mineralized albitites.

Fig. 4. Chondrite-normalized patterns in albitites, episyenite and granite samples of the Novokostantynivka deposit.

La/Yb ratio varies from 9.7 to 117.4 in the host granites with linear La-Ho correlation ($R^2=0,91$) (Fig. 5b). In albitites, La/Yb ratio ranges from 6.1 to 146.9, as in granites, however it is erratic, and no La-Yb correlation observed (Fig. 5b), indicating redistribution of REE during metasomatic alterations. On the other

hand, the amount of heavy REE + Y in the host Novoukrainka granites of the deposit is much lower (15.6...45.2 ppm) than in the Novoukrainka granites sampled outside the Novokostantynivka deposit (56.3...122.7 ppm), which obviously indicates spatial variations of REE concentration in granitic melts (Fig. 5c).

Fig. 5. Element interrelations in the Novokostantynivka deposit. a: Zr vs Hf; b: La vs Yb; c: U vs HREE+Y; d: Ho vs Y; a, b, d: 1 – albitites, 2 – episyenites, 3 – granites; c: 1 – granites in the deposit, 2 – granites out the deposit, 3 – episyenites, 4 – albitites, 5 – Zr > 350 ppm.

Y/Ho index varies between 24 and 34 when no fractionation between these two elements [7]. In host granites, Y/Ho ratios varies between 27.3 to 28.4, close to chondritic values 28.8 [5] with proportional changes of Y and Ho concentrations (Fig. 5d). Y/Ho ratios in albitites range more widely, from 24.0 up to 31.8, although well agree with linear correlation between Y and Ho in granites (Fig. 5d). In samples enriched in U by more than 2 wt.% and in samples with the highest concentrations of Y and Ho, Fig. 5d shows a slight disproportionation of Y-Ho.

Redistribution of REE during metasomatism is well observed by disproportionation of La and Yb (Fig. 5b). Also, Fig. 5c shows additional HREE concentration in ore bodies with U and Zr accumulation. HREE obviously incorporate into uraninite, brannerite and zircon-malacon.

Discussions and conclusions. Anomalously high concentrations of Zr with widespread zircon-malacon crystallization was described in mineralized Na-metasomatites in Ukraine [1]. For comparison, Zr/Hf ratios in the host metamorphic rocks of the Zhovta Richka deposit range from 35.7 to 50.9. High Zr concentrations

was also found in albitites of France [8] and thus is typical for Na-metasomatism and connected U-mineralization.

During magmatic processes, Zr and Hf are incredibly coherent, resulting from their similar ionic radii (72 and 71 pm respectively). In common rocks, they mostly accumulate in zircon with isomorphic incorporation of Hf instead of Zr. Bau [7] notes infractional Zr/Hf variations from 26 to 46. However, [9] and experiments of De Boer on separation of Hf from Zr in alkaline water solutions with carbonate crystallization [10] show a possibility of Zr-Hf fractionation. More alkaline Hf forms weaker complexes and thus precipitates as a solid faster during fractional carbonate crystallization than Zr having more stable soluble complexes. Consequently, acidization of the solution may result in a production of Zr-rich solutions. So, acidic pegmatites often contain hafnon [11] and cassiterite with below chondritic Zr/Hf ratio [12]. Wang et al. [13] described Hf-rich zircon in granitic pegmatites, and decreasing Zr/Hf ratio with granite differentiation. Thus, highly differentiated granitic melts where Hf enriched solids, would be a source of hydrothermal solutions with highly Zr/Hf ratios.

Zircon was unstable during formation of albite-ae-girine metasomatites and thus its precipitation as malacon is connected with later stages. Hydrothermal zircon mineralization accompanies andradite-titanite-epidote, actinolite-calcite and calcite-phlogopite parageneses of Ca-metasomatism and K-metasomatism of mineral-forming stages deposit. Strong Zr-U interrelation in the Novokostantynivka deposit (Fig. 3a) and common occurring paragenetic U-mineralization (brannerite and uraninite) and zircon-malacon (Fig. 2b) suggest that they crystallized simultaneously at least partially in the deposit. However, the highest Zr concentrations in the Zhovta Richka U deposit in Ukraine were found in metasomatically altered quartzite (up to 223.5) and barren Na-metasomatites (aegirinites and riebeckites – 101.7 and 154.5 respectively) [3]. Thus, possible redistribution and accumulation of Zr during Na-metasomatism is yet under question.

La/Yb ratio is a geochemical index showing fractionation of light REE from heavy REE. Linear correlation between La and Yb (Fig. 5b) records a strong control of REE fractionation by crystallization of mineral accessories during granitic melt cooling. Phosphates (monazite and apatite) and zircon are the major minerals hosting Y, REE, U and Th in the host granites. In metasomatic bodies, La-Yb dependence disappears (Fig. 5b) suggesting their erratic redistribution during metasomatism.

Rich U mineralization is the only visible input and accumulation of extrinsic REE from “uranium source” or a source of hydrothermal solutions, since U minerals have increased capacity in relation to heavy REE incorporation.

Suprachondritic Y/Ho ratios are characteristic of ‘marine’ environments, resulting from Ho precipitation from seawater when Y is stable in the soluble state [7]. Hydrothermal solutions are also commonly characterized by elevated Y/Ho ratios [14]. This suggests that the increase of Y concentration over Ho concentration in mineralized albitites is associated with their corresponding accumulation in hydrothermal minerals.

The proportional Y-Ho dependence is very stable at practically the same ratios in both granites and metasomatites (Fig. 5d). Only in rich uraninite ores it is somewhat prone to disproportionation. We attribute the increase in Y/Ho ratio in the most mineralized samples to the increase in Y/Ho ratio in hydrothermal solutions compared to the host granites, which should be a consequence of different geochemical behavior of these elements in aqueous solutions [7, 14].

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